

THE ROLE OF DEVELOPING THE INTEGRATION OF MUSICAL CREATIVITY AND SCIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article highlights the role and importance of musical creativity and science integration in the higher education system. Effective methods of combining creative and scientific activities in the process of music education based on modern pedagogical approaches are analyzed. The role of scientific and research activities in music education, mechanisms for directing music creators to use scientific achievements are considered. Also, the possibilities of increasing students' professional competence by developing the interaction between music and scientific knowledge are studied. The article offers recommendations aimed at increasing the effectiveness of creative education by combining musical knowledge with science and technology.

Keywords: musical creativity, science integration, higher education, pedagogical approaches, scientific and research activities, professional competence, music education, modern technologies, innovative approaches.

Introduction.

Music is the highest expression of the spiritual wealth of humanity, its culture, and it is not only an art, but also a phenomenon that combines thought, emotion, and science. In the modern higher education system, music is seen not only as a means of shaping creativity, but also as one of the important areas that ensure the scientific advancement of human thinking. As technologies are rapidly developing and integrating into all areas of education, deepening the relationship between music and science has become a pressing issue today.

Any creative process, including musical creativity, becomes more effective and meaningful when enriched with scientific achievements. For example, in modern higher education, not only musical knowledge, but also scientifically based approaches are widely taught through the use of multimedia technologies in music teaching, integration of disciplines such as sound engineering and acoustics. Therefore, the integration of music and science in the process of higher education serves as a solid foundation for the development of students'

professional competencies, the harmonization of their creative and scientific activities.

This article examines the interrelationship of music and science integration, its importance in the higher education system, and the possibilities of organizing this process more effectively. The issues of developing music education based on new methods and approaches in accordance with the requirements of the time are analyzed.

Methodology.

In order to effectively implement the integration of music and science in the process of higher education, a comprehensive methodological approach was used. The study combined the methods of theoretical analysis, experimental observation, and practical experience testing. Through this approach, the possibilities of identifying the interrelationship between music and science and successfully introducing this relationship into the educational process were investigated.

In the theoretical approach, advanced foreign and domestic experiences in music education, creative activity and science integration were analyzed. At the same time, the impact of modern pedagogical approaches and the use of innovative technologies in education on musical processes was studied. Special attention was paid to the selection and improvement of methods that ensure harmony between creative and scientific teaching methods in higher education. Within the framework of the practical approach, classes were organized to observe the processes of music education in higher educational institutions, develop the integration of musical creativity and science. During the study, integrative programs related to music technology, sound engineering and acoustics were developed and aimed at assessing what results they give in the development of students' creative and scientific abilities. As an important part of this study, feedback from students and teachers was collected through questionnaires and interviews. This process allowed us to identify how the integration of science and technology into music is perceived, existing problems and future opportunities.

At the same time, the results obtained using statistical analysis tools were deeply analyzed and the effectiveness of enriching musical creativity with scientific knowledge was determined. The methods developed as a result of the study were distinguished by their effectiveness in using modern technologies in music education, strengthening the scientific approach, and raising the professional training of students to a high level.

Discussion:

The importance of the integration of music creativity and science in higher education is increasing due to the requirements of modern education. As it was found during the study, enriching musical creativity with scientific achievements serves not only to strengthen musical knowledge and skills, but also to develop students' critical thinking skills. In today's era of globalization, it has become necessary for music education to move away from traditional methods and incorporate technologies and modern pedagogical approaches. The results of the study showed that the success of the integration of music and science largely depends on the methods used in the educational process. For example, combining music education with sound engineering, digital composition techniques, and multimedia technologies not only arouses interest among students, but also further expands their creative abilities. Also, integrated approaches allow students to be involved in research through musical creativity, which plays an important role in the development of their professional competencies. Among the problems identified during the discussion, it was noted that there is a lack of resources, qualified teachers, and modern technologies necessary for the implementation of integration in the higher education system. Many music curricula are still based on traditional methods, which can limit students' creativity. Therefore, there is a need to introduce research activities into the music education process and study advanced foreign experiences in this regard. However, on the positive side, experimental projects implemented on the integration of musical creativity and science in higher education have yielded results. Based on these projects, students' musical thinking has been further enriched, their creative approach and scientific interests have significantly increased. In addition, the possibility of increasing the efficiency of the musical educational process in higher educational institutions with the help of innovative approaches has been demonstrated.

Combining musical creativity with science not only improves the quality of the higher educational process, but also creates the basis for the development of students at the level of modern professional requirements. Therefore, creating the necessary conditions for expanding the integration of musical creativity and science in the higher education system remains an urgent task.

Conclusion.

The integration of musical creativity and science is one of the modern educational approaches that opens up new prospects in the higher education system. This integration not only enriches the content of musical education, but

also serves to develop the creative abilities of students and equip them with modern scientific knowledge. This study once again proves that music is not just an art form, but also a force that elevates human thinking in harmony with science.

The results of the study showed that for the successful introduction of musical creativity and science integration into the educational process, it is important to enrich educational programs with modern pedagogical technologies. The use of multimedia platforms, digital music technologies and scientific research methods makes the musical education process more effective. As a result, not only the creative abilities of students, but also their interest in critical thinking, scientific research and practical activities will increase. However, the problems encountered in this process cannot be denied. Factors such as lack of resources, shortage of qualified personnel and insufficient introduction of technologies in some regions can slow down progress in this area. Therefore, it is necessary to provide state support, retrain pedagogical personnel and expand research projects to develop the integration of musical creativity and science in the higher education system. In conclusion, the integration of musical creativity and science should be recognized as an effective direction for introducing innovations in the higher education process. This approach serves to form students not only as creative people, but also as modern knowledgeable specialists. This harmony between music and science is important as a solid foundation for the spiritual and scientific advancement of man. Therefore, research and practical experiments in this area should be continued and expanded.

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